

lecture form of studying the material does not exceed 20%, in the business game - up to 90%. Experimental data of H. E. Meichner confirm the superiority of interactive methods in the educational process. He said that learners remember 10% of what they read, 20% of what they hear, 30% of what they see, 50% of what they hear and see, and when they actively receive information, they remember 80% of what they say, and 90% of what they do.

Interactive activity in the classroom involves the organization and development of dialogic communication, which leads not only to mutual understanding and interaction, but also to the joint solution of common and important tasks for each participant. During dialogic learning, students learn not only critical thinking, situation analysis and solving complex problems based on relevant information, but also weigh alternative opinions, make thoughtful decisions, participate in discussions and communicate with other people. When using interactive methods, when students search for truth collectively, the observed competition has a great impact on intellectual activity.

During the development of scientific and technical progress, the amount of information necessary for mastering is increasing. Information quickly becomes outdated and needs constant updating. In this regard, training aimed at memorizing the material in memory and retaining the learned material can meet modern requirements. This is the problem of forming the qualities of thinking that allow the student to learn a constant stream of new information on his own, to

develop abilities that will be preserved after the completion of education and ensure the ability of a person to stay abreast of the accelerated scientific and technical progress. There is a need for new methods and methods of teaching that teach students to learn, that is, to find and learn the necessary information independently. The teacher's role is to draw conclusions about the student's work and to point out mistakes during the execution of tasks.

References

1. Florentina L.N. (2019) Teaching-interactive method used in the teaching-learning process // International Journal of Educational Sciences. No. 1, Year 1/2019. http://peijes.com/gallery/no.1-year1-2019-proedu_nae-florentina.pdf
2. Kutbiddinova R.A., Eromasova A.A., Romanova M.A. (2016) The use of interactive methods in the educational process of the higher education institution // International journal of environmental & science education, VOL. 11, NO. 14. - P. 6557-6572. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1115891.pdf>
3. Alkozhaeva N.S., Tolshova U.B. Application of new pedagogical technologies in the educational process of the higher school: Educational tool. - Almaty: Kazakh University, 2009. - 126 p.
4. Marina V. Vinogradova, Lyubov I. Yakobyuk, Natalia V. Zenina (2018) Interactive teaching as an effective method of pedagogical interaction // Revista espacios. Vol. 39 (Number 30) Year 2018. Page 25- 33. <https://www.revistaespacios.com/a18v39n30/a18v39n30p25.pdf>

THE ROLE AND PLACE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN THE CURRENT EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract

The article discusses interactive methods and the significance of their role and place in the modern educational process, the features of their application, the general results and effects of interactive learning. The necessity of using interactive teaching methods is considered, emphasizing their important role in improving the quality of education. There will be kinds of active learning methods. Modern teaching methods are noted and a brief summary of their content is given. The experimentally revealed features of the attitude of high school students to the activity of perception and interpretation of the author's text and writing an essay based on what they have read are described, the reasons for their difficulties are identified. Features of interactive methods, their advantages, the activities of the teacher and student in the context of interactive learning. Ways to improve the efficiency of the process of working on text activities in high school are described and numerous examples of interactive exercises and tasks for students are given, which can be used both in computer science lessons and as part of elective courses, in extracurricular activities. The article includes the development of role-playing games, cases, quest.

Keywords: interactive teaching methods, role-playing games, demonstration, work in small groups, discussion, technique, training, interactive, practice, innovation.

The growth of spiritual and material needs of society creates the need to increase the level of social maturity of society members, their readiness for dialogue and self-knowledge. In this regard, the current educational process cannot be based on an educational approach. Today, everyone knows the importance of

teaching schoolchildren to think, understand, and act. Therefore, interactive learning methods, i.e. «methods of purposeful enhanced intersubjective interaction between the teacher and students to create optimal conditions for their development» are of particular relevance. Interactive methods, in particular, group discussion,

snowball, business games, project method, etc. belongs to. It is known that interactive methods are based on enhanced interaction of all participants in the educational process. Interaction is a philosophical category that shows the processes of objects influencing each other, their interdependence, and the generation of one object by another object. Considering interaction as a development factor, A.V. Mudrova, communicating with people and society, a person «not only knows himself well in comparison with others, but also gains new experience in actions and relationships», realizes «his inner potential» and complements them in structure, content, value. writes.

Along with the concept of interactive teaching methods, related terms are used in scientific literature. In order not to get confused in their use, we define some concepts. Taking into account that the form is the type, structure of something depending on the content, set and volume of certain components, interactive forms of education include training, business game, organizational form of extracurricular work, interactive lesson and the lesson using it. Interactive learning, compared to traditional learning, we consider learning in which interactive forms and methods prevail. T.S. Panina, According to L.N.Vavilova, interactive learning technologies are a set of forms, methods, methods, and tools that include collective thinking.

Interactive learning is characterized by a significant change in the nature of the relationship between the teacher and students compared to

traditional forms of learning: the student becomes the subject of this process, and the teacher becomes its organizer; in the form of study, business, role-playing games, debates, new experience is mastered and new knowledge is gained. Usually, its implementation involves working in small groups and creating an environment of dialogue. The fundamental difference between interactive learning and the classical form of the educational process is that the participants of group interaction go through misunderstanding, discussion, comparison, analysis, and as a result understanding and mastery in the way organized by the teacher, and passing this way is possible only in the mode of cooperation and constant reflection. According to S. B. Stupina, interactivity is a way of cognition, implemented in the form of joint activities of students, all participants in the educational process interact with each other, exchange information, jointly solve problems, model situations, evaluate the actions of colleagues and their own behavior, plunge into a real atmosphere of business cooperation in solving problems. S.B. Stupina named the following as the principles of interactive learning:

- dialogic interaction;
- work in small groups based on cooperation;
- active role-playing game.

In general, the differences between interactive learning and the classical form can be presented in the form of a table (Table 1).

Table 1

Comparison of traditional and interactive learning tasks.

Traditional learning	Interactive learning
The task of the teacher is to impart and assimilate as much knowledge as possible to the students	The task of the teacher is to create conditions in which students themselves discover, master and construct their knowledge
The task of learners is to reproduce as fully as possible the knowledge created by others	The task of students is to learn to study, learn to live, learn to live together, learn responsibility

The project method appeared in the USA at the beginning of the 20th century (J. Dewey, W.H. Kilpatrick). Around 1910, the case method appeared at the Harvard University Business School in the USA, it was used in Russia in the 1990s and became popular in the 21st century.

The "Brainstorming" method appeared in the USA in the 30s of the 20th century. In the 20s and 30s of the 20th century, design, laboratory-team methods, industrial and labor excursions, and experiments were actively used in the USSR. In the 80s of the 20th century, the spread of game types of interactive learning is associated with the activities of the Moscow methodological interdisciplinary seminar (G.P. Shchedrovitsky, etc.), organizational and active games appear. In the 70s and 80s, V.K. Tarasov's school of educational games, E.V. Gilbo's emotional-game methodology, role-playing games in training, and business games in pedagogy became popular. The 90s are distinguished by the development of intensive business games on decision-making and regional issues.

The theories of personal activation and interactive learning are devoted to the works of many scientists (N.P. Enikeeva, A.A. Verbitsky, M.V. Klarin, I.Ya. Lerner, A.M. Matyushkin, P.I. Pidkasisty, E.S. Polat, N.F. Talizina, T.L. Chepel, S.A. Shmakov and others). Researchers are interested in the issue of application in the practice of higher schools, however, interactive technologies may have a suitable place in the space of a general education school, but the issue of their use within the teaching of individual school subjects has not yet been fully covered in the works of psychologists, teachers, and methodologists.

As experience shows, schoolchildren actively participate in project activities and have a positive attitude to the use of the project method when studying a certain subject, gladly respond to teachers' suggestions regarding the organization of educational games, brainstorming, and group discussions. It should be noted that the effectiveness of its use in school conditions is determined by the quality of didactic material and the choice of methods according to the age characteristics and capabilities of students. Therefore, traditional forms, approaches, and methods for interactive teaching should

be adapted to the conditions of the educational process of the school.

Considering the value of interactive teaching methods, researchers identify its main features. So, S.S. Kashlev talks about the following properties of interactive learning:

- activities of mutual training and collective thinking of participants;
- equal rights of each participant in the discussion of the subject under study;
- real life problems and situations are considered as the subject of study;
- the main thing is to gain new experience, dialogue, analyze emerging contradictions, consciously create new meanings for themselves, exchange meanings.

Participating in an interactive lesson, each participant of collective learning directly interacts with the

object of knowledge, it is in an active mode, lives and experiences certain situations modeled according to its real image and similarity. The active participation of everyone in the process of mastering educational material increases cognitive motivation, students master the skills of successful communication and independent learning, learn to take responsibility for joint and individual actions to achieve results, and develop reflective skills.

Interactive methods of teaching correspond to the tasks of the person-oriented approach, because in the conditions of joint activity and enhanced communicative activity, the student's personality is revealed, his abilities are revealed. Compared to traditional teaching, the content and forms of the student's activities change in the classroom. The activity of the student in the case of use is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Student activity in the case of using interactive teaching methods

The teacher acts as a moderator of the learning process (regulates the learning situation, regulates the process of division of tasks in the group, manages the learning process, involves each student in group activities, organizes and directs reflective activities) and its facilitator. E.L. Yerokhina, a facilitator-teacher, is a teacher who believes in cooperation with the student and is able to empathize. Its task is to stimulate

students' activity, help them to find a solution to the learning problem, encourage them to this solution, provide support, use methods of constructive criticism and approval. Adhering to a democratic style of communication, the facilitator is passionate about joint activities with students, treats them with kindness and shows genuine interest in the results of the learning process.

Figure 2 - Teacher's activity in the case of using interactive teaching methods

Compared to passive teaching methods, when the teacher acts as a translator of knowledge and experience, interactive teaching methods have the following advantages:

- students' interest in the taught subject is awakened, it develops due to participation in group work and communication process, increases their enthusiasm for learning activity, research, creativity;
- learning material is learned more effectively, because the student is influenced by what he experienced during interaction with other participants of the process;
- participation in collective consultation is usually highly effective, the product of its activity is distinguished by its quality, innovation, originality, and completeness;
- a sense of responsibility arises in the student, because he understands that his choice can determine the result of collective activity, the level of self-awareness increases, especially if the student's proposal is supported by other members, he strives for independence, because the teacher does not offer a ready-made solution to the educational task set before him, but to discover the way of knowledge and action. encourages;

- teaches behavior in case of change of social roles and change of circumstances;
- the interests of different subjects may collide and, if necessary, responsible choice forms critical thinking and the ability to make decisions in non-standard situations;
- students learn to interact in a group, to work together, to be patient, to respect human dignity, to recognize everyone's right to freedom of speech;
- emotional intelligence of students is developed;
- students develop a value relationship to the team, the whole society, learn to recognize and formulate their own assessment, opinion, point of view, and compare with others;
- formation of metadisciplinary skills (goal setting, planning, classification, representation of actions and results, etc.) and universal educational activities (regulatory, cognitive, communicative) are carried out;
- interactive teaching methods are a type of feedback tool that allows the teacher to diagnose the reaction of students to the educational process and draw conclusions;

– conditions are created for pedagogical monitoring: the teacher can identify new trends in the behavior of students, identify leaders, notice negative manifestations in time.

Attempts to classify interactive forms and methods of teaching are known in the science of pedagogy. For example, T.S. Panina, L.N. Vavilova offers the following types of interactive teaching methods: discussion (dialogue, group discussion, analysis of situations from experience); game (didactic and creative games, including business and role-playing, organizational and active games); training forms (communicative trainings, sensitivity trainings). However, the authors themselves indicate that teaching forms can include discussion and game teaching methods. Therefore, taking into account some illogicality of this classification due to the mixing of forms and teaching methods in it, we divide interactive teaching methods into discussions and games.

The use of interactive teaching methods is effective if a number of conditions are met. In particular:

1. The content of the activities proposed by the teacher should be interesting for students; their curiosity arises when they see the practical importance of the experience they have gathered and find themselves in a situation of discovery.

2. The environment in which the activity takes place should be organized in a special way: students should be placed in such a way that they can communicate, and the teacher can move between them; the material equipment of the lesson should be suitable for drawing (markers, flip chart, blackboard), showing work results (projector, laptop, etc.).

3. The teacher should create a special atmosphere in the group characterized by everyone's genuine interest, desire and ability to enter the polylogue.

4. In the lesson, the student should be in a successful situation when he receives approval individually or in a group. Assessments given to the actions of one or another participant should be positive, the methods of criticism used should be constructive and serve to improve the product of joint activity and the development of the student as a subject of the educational process.

5. Each participant must follow the rules of group work suggested by the teacher or put forward by the group at the beginning of the work. They may relate to diligence, goodwill, constructive criticism, engagement, honesty and openness, and recognition of

everyone's right to make mistakes. Often, moderator-teachers recommend the rule of "here and now", which consists of setting the task, understanding, generating ideas, drawing up conclusions right now; the rule of the "I principle" aimed at rejecting negligent communication, constantly projecting the lived moment onto one's own experience, the picture of the world.

6. A prerequisite for the effectiveness of using interactive methods of teaching is the representation of actions and results.

There are a number of difficulties and disadvantages of using interactive teaching methods in the classroom at school, which are primarily the poor development of the theoretical foundations of the use of forms and methods of interactive teaching, insufficient methodological and technical support for the use of interactive teaching, teachers' lack of readiness to work in conditions of complex interaction with a group. Some technologies require the creation of special props to decorate the school, which takes a lot of time. The teacher must overcome the task of forming and maintaining a high level of motivation of students, which gives him additional responsibility. Also, some students who are characterized by increased excitability, demonstrative behavior patterns, and intemperance have problems with participation in these forms: they require a special approach from the teacher. The competitive atmosphere, emotional impact, characteristic of the game methods, unfortunately, can cause anxiety among some students, which is full of the use of unethical behavior methods. In order to prevent this, the teacher must be able to overcome non-standard situations and resolve ethical disputes. Therefore, the use of interactive methods of teaching requires a lot of work for the teacher.

References

1. Kutbiddinova R.A., Eromasova A.A., Romanova M.A. (2016) The use of interactive methods in the educational process of the higher education institution // *International journal of environmental & science education*, VOL. 11, NO. 14. - P. 6557-6572. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1115891.pdf>
2. Nikolaevna K.O., Dolieva S.F. & Isanbayevna Y.G. (2021) The role of interactive teaching methods in the formation of students' professional competence // *Linguistics and Culture Review*, 5(S2). - P. 1424-1430. <https://doi.org/10.21744/lingcure.v5nS2.1958>
3. Ashurova Sanobar Yuldashevna (2019) Importance of interactive teaching methods in professional education // *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences* Vol. 7 No. 12. – P. 666-670.